

**MAGNETIC RESONANCE IMAGING IN THE ASSESSMENT OF
RISK FACTORS OF URINARY INTENTION AFTER RADICAL
PROSTATECTOMY**

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Background. The quality of life of patients with prostate cancer (PCa) after radical prostatectomy (RP) significantly depends on the occurrence of such a complication as urinary incontinence. Identification of risk factors at the preoperative stage will make it possible to reduce the likelihood of this complication. The use of magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) for this purpose seems to be a promising direction.

Materials and methods. In 56 patients with prostate cancer, before RP, MRI was performed at the Republican specialized oncology and radiology scientific-practical medical center and private clinic using the MR750 device (General Electric, USA) with a magnetic field strength of 3 T to determine the length of the membranous urethra and the shape of the apex of the prostate glands. The length of the membranous urethra was measured in the frontal and sagittal planes. The shape of the apex of the prostate gland was determined by evaluating its relationship with the external urethral sphincter in the sagittal MRI. There were four variants of the structure of the apex of the prostate gland: form A - the tip covered the sphincter of the urethra circularly; form B - the tip covered the urethral sphincter in front; form C - the tip covered the sphincter of the urethra from behind the Congress of the world oncologists form D - the tip did not cover the sphincter of the urethra at all. The median postoperative follow-up was 8 months (3-6 months).

Research results. The frequency of urinary incontinence after RP was 6.9 %. The length of the membranous urethra ranged from 7 to 22 mm (median 13 mm). With the length of the membranous urethra ≤ 12 mm urinary incontinence was detected in (15 patients), 26.7% cases, 13-14 mm (18 patients) – 31.1%, >14 mm (33 patients) - 58.9%. The greatest difference in the relative risk (RR) of urinary incontinence after RP was noted when patients were graded into two categories depending on the following values of the length of the membranous urethra: [≤ 14 mm] and [> 14 mm]. The RR was 2.20 (94% confidence interval - 1.91-2.53)

Conclusions: After radical prostatectomy to assessment risk factors of urinary intention the role of MRI is associated with significantly more rapid return of urinary continence after surgery.

